

Research Article

Factors Influence Social Media Crime Among Young Generations

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Abstract: Social media crime has received the greatest attention and has become a hot topic that is constantly rising as children, tweens, and teens use and accessibility of Internet networks has increased, exposing them to numerous types of social media crime. Therefore, this research paper aims to summarize, analyze, and disclose the findings and factors which influence awareness of social media crime among the young generation to protect their future as well as the country. A structured literature methodology was implemented to analyze and explore 22 previous studies from the UiTM EzAccess online database that are relevant to the aspects that affect social media crime among young generations while conducting this research article. The crucial analysis of the literature reveals that several aspects influence social media crime among young generations, including the type of social media crime, the factors, the impact, and the strategy of social media to influence the young generation. This research is one of several that provide a comprehensive review of the literature on the rising issue of factors that influence social media crime in the context of the young generation. Thus, in this structured literature analysis, further awareness in combating social media crime among the younger generations can be identified.

Keywords: factors influence; social media; crime; young generations; literature review.

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1. INTRODUCTION

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, social media is a website, computer program, and kind of media that allows people to interact and exchange information via computers or smartphones over the Internet. In a nutshell, social media is the largest and most advanced digital medium that allows individuals and organizations to create, share, and exchange any kind of text, or multimedia such as images, videos, or voice recordings, as well as communicate with other users via voice calls or video calls over existing Internet networks and virtual communities. Nowadays, social media encompasses many forms, including messaging applications, social networks, blogs, forums, and more. It is well known that the most popular social media sites users frequently use include WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, and so forth. This fundamental social media function normally features and distributes all material provided by users, as well as personalized profiles representing those people, allowing users to participate in standard social media activities such as sharing, likes, reviews, and

discussions. People join social media sites to interact and communicate with others, to share their thoughts, experiences, or good things, to learn new things like tips and tutorials, and to stay updated with the newest hot news and market trends.

Smartphones and the Internet may be highly beneficial tools for the growth of teenagers, allowing them to stay in contact with family and friends while also providing numerous learning possibilities (Álvarez-García et al., 2019). Children, tweens, teens, adults, and the elderly are all among today's social media users. One in every three Internet users worldwide is a child or teenager under the age of 18 (UNICEF, 2017). Although social media is widely seen to provide several benefits in numerous aspects of life, keep in mind that nothing is perfect in today's world since anything that has advantages also has disadvantages. According to the Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research (MFMER), youngsters can be severely impacted by social media use, which can distract them, interrupt their sleep, and expose them to bullying, rumor spreading, inaccurate views of other people's lives, and peer pressure. Tweens (ages 8 to 12) increased their daily screen time to five hours and 33 minutes, up from four hours and 44 minutes, while teenagers (ages 13 to 18) increased their daily screen time to eight hours and 39 minutes, up from seven hours and 22 minutes (Moyer, 2022). Therefore, a situation like this might expose the younger generation to various forms of social media criminality. With more screen time for the younger population, there will be more involvement in social media crimes such as bullying, harassment, stalking, stealing information and accounts, and receiving threats online. Without solutions as well as awareness from themselves, parents, social media management, or the government, there is no hesitation that this issue will become more prominent in the future.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The literature review approach in the present research. Due to the prior study's use as a reference, such research methodology is employed to ensure of research technique is employed to make sure the author can carefully complete this research article. The research's materials include publications that were analyzed from a variety of sources and databases, including Academics Journal, Societies, International Journal, IEEE Explore, Emerald Insight, ProQuest, and Google Scholar. Previous research has demonstrated that social media exposure has a major impact on the public's view of crime, particularly among young individuals (Trninić et al., 2021).

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Economic Times (2023) has defined the term 'social media' as websites and programs that help people talk to each other, get involved, share information, and work together. Merriam-Webster dictionary also defined 'social media' as a form of electronic communication such as websites for social networking and microblogging through which users create online communities to share information, ideas, personal messages, and other contents, meanwhile the term 'crime' has been defined as an illegal act for which someone can be punished by the government. Macmillan Dictionary has defined 'young generations' as the youngest adults in society.

The peak of social media crime started during the pandemic of Coronavirus where it started normalizing people using the technologies as their norms. It shows that during Covid-19, parents' religious behaviors lead to teenagers' behavior on the Internet, especially towards cybercrime (Li, Li, Fang & Wang, 2021). In most developing countries, many of them are not concerned about the policy literature regarding social media which leads to crime existence (Asongu, Nwachukwu, Orim & Pyke, 2019). Most problematic teenagers are using multiple public and private social media platforms such as Facebook, Snapchat, Twitter, and YouTube as early signs of fear of missing out (FOMO) and phubbing behavior which slowly leads to cybercrime (Apoorva, Chaudhuri, Hussain, & Chatterjee, 2022). The openness behavior on social media including revealing private information brings an effect on cognitive behavior which brings risks to security and visibility and exposure to fraud (Murthy and Gopalkrishnan, 2022). Insufficient information and lack of knowledge among teenagers due to cultural

poverty leads to social damage leads to a social emergency. Comparison between peers, media illiterate among parents, and less social skills will lead to crime in social media among children (Amini & Pashootanzadeh, 2019).

Moreover, teenagers' habit of video sharing on social media negatively impacts privacy limitations and allows access to personal information retrieval (Kang, Shiu & Hwang 2021). The behavioral intention toward cybercrime among students is mainly due to attitude, social norms, perceived behavioral control, excessive usage of social media, fewer parenting controls, and lack of regulations and knowledge (Alotaibi, 2019). Other than that, it is found that teenagers who experience psychosocial distress during their childhood may be likely to develop abnormalities in online social interaction as they see online violence as less threatening and more rewarding, compared to other types of interactions (Al-Samarraie, Bello, Alzahrani, Smith, & Emele, 2021). In addition, the modern criminal is targeting young users who have influence or have a high number of followers since most of them are less concerned about security and privacy (Cengiz, Kalem & Boluk, 2022). Therefore, it is found that teenagers that have a high privacy self-efficacy behavior tend to have a greater concern about online privacy compared to others. Self-efficacy helps the user to gain more general respect and ethics towards the technology's regulations. (Baker-Eveleth & Stone, 2021).

Not only that, but social media crime also can turn into sexual harassment as the exposure to dating apps to minimize, legitimize and excuse sexual harm are the core factors towards sexual harassment (Cama, 2021). The development of the web and technology also leads to minor exploitation where cyber libertarians or Internet hackers have brutally breached human rights which leads to serious child protection-related crime (Salter & Hanson, 2021). The interactions of teenagers through technology may involve sexism and racism which affect young people's being, becoming, and belonging to future identities (H€allgren & Bj€ork, 2022). It has also been found that most social media crime in youth the ones who have less relationship bonding between family members, and they have a higher exposure towards social media crime (Nalaka & Diunugala, 2020). Social media crime turns out more critical when it involves nonsensual circulated media which leads to traumas, especially for female teenagers (Gjika, 2020).

Social Media Disorders are one of the long-term impacts on the victims if they are experiencing a significant negative impact relating to social media crime (Norwood, 2022). Social media nowadays also normalizes hashtags some of them publicly posting photos and media of minors and teenagers. As it is simply seen as safe, it is encouraging criminals for cybercrime activities such as illegal editing, fake accounts, and digital kidnapping (Bare, 2020).

4. FINDINGS

There are a variety of factors that influence social media crime among the young generation that has been obtained by reading and study from several papers collected from various online databases. The overview of social media crime, factors contributing to social media crime among the young generation, impacts of social media crime on young generations, and the strategy of social media for young generations from diverse parties on social media are covered in these research findings.

4.1 Overview of social media crime

Khoury, G. (2019) has concluded online threats, stalks, cyberbullying, hacking and fraud, illegal purchasing, vacation robberies, and fake online friendships as examples of social media crime. Harness, J. (2023) also stated that some common types of social media are bullying, false impersonation, stalking, hacking, phishing and fraud, sex crimes, illegal business, vacation robberies, illegal media sharing, and getting caught in social media. As reported by the India National Crime Reporting Bureau, statistics on crime cases on social media show that it has elevated by 43% in 2018, from 27,248 cases to 44,546 cases in 2019 (Agrawal, S., 2021).

A study conducted by a research agency in Europe has found that YouTube, Instagram, WhatsApp, TikTok, and Snapchat are the most common social media downloaded by teenagers and it is found that approximately most teenagers spend 4 to 7 hours a day on phone (Milmo, D., 2022). A survey conducted for 40,000 respondents worldwide by RR Author (2022) justified that 68.44% of teenagers agreed that they are more engaged in social media than any other age group, 37% agreed that Facebook is the most popular social media platform and 39.5% agreed that an average of teenagers will have more than 5 social accounts each. Moyer, M. W. (2022) explained based on a survey published by Common-Sense Media, a non-profit research organization, in the year 2021 has shown an increment of 17% from 2019 the cumulative screen time among teens and tweens and the increment is still growing for the next four years. On average, the tweens had spent 5 hours and 33 minutes daily and teens had spent 7 hours and 22 minutes daily.

4.2 Factors contributing to social media crime among the young generation

The younger generation, tweens, and teenagers are active users of social media nowadays. Today's youngsters spend a lot of time on social media rather than on productive activities (Rani & Padmalosani, 2019). In simple words, they are the direct product of the world of digitization at this point. Among the factors of social media crime towards the young generation is the anonymity of the Internet, lack of validation of social media content, and lack of parental control. These social media crimes range from cyberbullying, online fraud, online harassment, identity theft, and so forth.

All these crimes are often caused by the anonymity of the Internet which makes the social media users act without fear of what the consequences will be. The unrestricted expansion of anonymous identities, on the other hand, has weaponized the Internet, transforming it into a real orgy of hatred, violence, vitriol, and intimidation (Tewari, 2022). This factor is extremely serious since anonymity encourages anti-social behavior, and the use of fake names, fake identification (ID), and unverified user accounts allow people to disguise their identity when they post inappropriate messages and comments. In addition, the validation of social media content, most of which are established companies handling social media are constantly struggling to constantly monitor activities, censor content and remove such harmful content by use of users of different ages. Next is the lack of parental control over children's social media use. Nevertheless, things posted to social media that are deemed unsuitable or constitute a risk to users must be checked and deleted, even if this takes time. Live-stream footage of mass shootings and viral social media "challenges" that inspire young people to commit risky acts like holding their breath until they pass out are examples of content that might be restricted under the new rules (Kurohi & Low, 2022). Dorasamy et al. (2021) also highlighted the need for parental involvement in children's Internet safety. Parents are unable to spend time with their children since they are preoccupied with their daily responsibilities. Social Internet allows youngsters of today to escape boredom (Rani & Padmalosani, 2019). Therefore, parents may not be aware of the harmful risks associated with social media and their children's social media monitoring activities are not carried out. Nevertheless, parental control, however limited and indirect, has a protective impact against cyber victimization (Álvarez-García et al., 2019).

Thus, it can be seen that all of these factors not only contribute to the exposure of children and adolescents to online predators but also indirectly engage them with other types of social media crimes. According to Rashidah Abdul Rahman & Normah Omar (2015) as well, educating young people about cybercrime will assist to raise awareness and perceptions of cybercrime.

4.3 Impact of social media crime on young generations

Social media crime toward teenagers has shown several negative impacts. Unethical use of social media will lead to youth crime. Online crime in young generations such as stalking and intimate partner violence, human trafficking, online pornography, minor abuse imagery, and online hate and harassment are targeting female teenagers as their victims (Bailey and Shayan, 2021).

For the long-term effect, these victims will suffer from mental illnesses such as depression and social anxiety. Normally these patients are scared to seek for help, and it is suggested to develop a new approach to improve their help-seeking behaviors (Goodwin and Behan, 2023). RR Author (2022) claims that the youth tend to suffer from poor mental conditions, resulting in fewer physical activities and interactions with people. Social media crime affects the teen's emotional, mental, and physical health as they can suffer from FOMO (fear of missing out) problems, depression, and anxiety also includes intentional physical harm towards the victim, (Agrawal, S., 2021). Glazzard, J. & Stones, S. (2019) summarize that social media bullying and body image concerns have a significant effect on mental health among young people. It brings negative development as it can influence anxiety, stress, and depression. Social media bully can also be in the form of humiliating messages and media which leads to embarrassment and confidence loss.

Social media crime also leads to violence in human rights and privacy rights. Human right is recognized by protecting one's dignity and privacy from abuse, discrimination, and potentially dangerous activities. Social media infringement such as stalking and illegal monitoring will against the human rights of teenagers (Coombs, 2021). Privacy rights cases can relate to identity theft and cyberstalking. The perpetrator may have collected the identifiable information with improper use for their purpose. The perpetrator also acts in the form of stalking the victim's social media which produces discomfort or abuse (Thukral, P. & Kainya, V., 2022). Identity theft is also threatening in social networking as it can utilize a person's personal data illegally such as mobile numbers and addresses to demand confidential information. Profile cloning attack is one of the new crimes that exist as the assaulter creates a cloned social media profile to build trust and connections to attack silently through cyberstalking and blackmailing (Jain, A. K., Sahoo, S. R., & Kaubiyal, J. (2021).

4.4 The strategy of social media for young generations

The use of social media to draw young people's attention is known as a social media strategy for the younger generation. The social media algorithm, advertisements, and the demands of young people on social media are three of them.

A social media algorithm is a system of guidelines and cues that automatically classifies content on a social network by the likelihood that each particular social media user would engage and enjoy it (Newberry, 2022). The content that news readers are exposed to more frequently is stuff that has been chosen using an algorithm. In particular, the younger generations, who depend on social media websites like Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram for individualized news. 2019 (Kalogeropoulos). Therefore, algorithms are beginning to affect how young people learn about their environment more and more. However, little is known about how people see and engage with automated news selection. Numerous conceptual studies (e.g., Beer, 2017; Diakopoulos, 2015; Willson, 2017) have investigated how algorithms impact daily life, but these often adopt a technological approach to ascertain how algorithms wield power.

The social network, a cutting-edge new media, is currently helping marketers and consumers increase their communication. This is the most recent development in product advertising and customer outreach. Facebook is one of the social networking sites with the fastest growth. It takes a lot of spontaneous brainstorming among the network's participants for an opinion to emerge in the media (Akar & Topcu, 2011; Kim & Ko, 2012). In actuality, this complete social media platform has made it feasible for any brand to sell its goods through exposure, attention, and perception, as well as to create opinions and establish values (Kim & Ko, 2010).

Moreover, since social media is utilized for amusement and self-expression, young people who use it must employ this strategy. Furthermore, the platform may enlighten children about current events, facilitate cross-border dialogue, and transmit information on several issues, including healthy behaviors. Teenagers may also benefit from significant connections with peers and a big social network, as well as from hilarious or disturbing social media (Mayo, 2022).

5. DISCUSSION

First, studies on people's fear of crime were created and advanced by researchers. Due to its distinct features and the current growth in user numbers, social media was the researcher's primary platform of choice (Greenwood et al., 2016; Perrin, 2015). examined the impact of social media use on society's perceptions of victimization and criminal fear. The findings imply that young individuals' total use of social media has a significant impact on how miserable they feel. This result backs up the claims made in the cultivation research.

The findings suggest that using social media more frequently may amplify the psychological and social factors that cause fear, which is consistent with earlier studies (Kross et al., 2013; Martin et al., 2012; O'Keeffe & Clarke-Pearson, 2011) that linked frequent social media use to negative effects like anxiety and social withdrawal. Fear of crime was not associated with any aspects of traditional or entertainment media, with the possible exception of watching national television news, which was only weakly associated. Despite the possibility that this contradicts earlier efforts, social media is eventually a more significant and effective media source (Callanan, 2012; Chiricos et al., 2000, 1997; Dowler, 2003; Eschholz et al., 2003; Jamieson & Romer, 2014; Kohm et al., 2012). This is true because it has a higher likelihood of being used by young people than mainstream media that focuses on amusement. A sample of college students who claimed to use social media more regularly than any other kind of conventional media on average serves as evidence of this.

Not only that, youth can share their writing, writing-related content, and other works via social media (Mesch, 2009; Shewmaker, 2012). This demonstrates how social media can simultaneously meet young people's demands for relationship development and provide them with a special chance to participate in the media actively (Mesch, 2009)

Furthermore, there are benefits to using social media, although it is not always all positive. Keeping in touch with friends and family is one of them. You can maintain contact with far-flung friends and family members by using social media. You can use social media to organize parties and get-togethers as well as to share pictures, videos, and updates about your life. Besides that, developing relationships can connect with people who share your interests through social media. You may interact with people you might not otherwise meet on social media by connecting with them in groups and communities. The next positive is acquiring new knowledge. Social networking may be a fantastic resource for knowledge and education. On several subjects, you can find articles, videos, and other resources.

Additionally, receiving support is another positive. Social networking may be a terrific resource for finding comfort through trying times. You can make connections with other individuals who have gone through similar things, and you can find tools and knowledge to make it through. And finally, doing good. An excellent method to give back to your community is through social media. You can donate your time to causes that matter to you, and you can utilize social media to spread the word about significant concerns. The use of social media, of course, also has certain drawbacks. It's critical to be informed of these dangers and to utilize social media responsibly and safely.

6. CONCLUSION

In modern days, social media is one of the essential things, especially for young generations as they can gain a lot of knowledge and information. Thukral, P. & Kainya, V. (2022) states that social networking sites help the young generations to keep updated with the information worldwide limitless and help them in term of educational purpose. Social networking also helps the young generations to express their thoughts and ideas to the world resulting in a convenient and pleasurable space in social media.

According to several studies, while young people are typically aware of the hazards of social media crime, they may not always be aware of the exact types of crimes that can occur or how to defend themselves. These findings show that young people need more education and knowledge regarding social media crime. Parents, schools, and social media corporations may all play a part in educating young people about the dangers of social media and how to protect themselves. There is some advice for parents and educators on how to talk to their children about cybercrime on social media. To begin, talk to your youngster about the various sorts of social media crimes that might occur. Make it clear that cyberbullying, online predators, and other forms of social media crime can have serious consequences in people's life. After that, assist your child in developing safe Internet behaviors. This includes things like creating secure passwords, exercising caution when sharing information online, and not responding to messages from strangers. Next, encourage your youngster to alert a trusted adult to any unusual behavior. This could be a parent, teacher, counselor, or another trusted adult.

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